

Stage-Wise Divergence Detection: A Diagnostic Framework for Closing Real-Time vs. Offline Accuracy Gaps in ERP-Based Brain-Computer Interfaces

Khanh-Dung Tran Rayo Lab Pte Ltd¹ E-mail: dung@therayo.com

Keywords: brain-computer interface, P300 speller, online-offline gap, real-time validation, preprocessing pipeline, signal divergence, Euclidean alignment

Abstract

Objective: Brain-computer interfaces (BCIs) based on event-related potentials (ERPs) exhibit accuracy degradation when offline-trained classifiers are deployed in real-time streaming environments. The online-offline gap is widely acknowledged but lacks a systematic diagnostic methodology. We present a stage-wise divergence detection framework that decomposes the preprocessing chain into six ordered stages and injects comparison probes at each boundary to localize signal-path mismatches.

Approach: The framework instruments the ERP preprocessing pipeline at six stages (A–F: raw epoch slicing, bandpass filtering, baseline correction, Euclidean Alignment, channel reordering, trial-level scoring). Pearson correlation and L2-ratio metrics quantify divergence between offline and real-time paths at each stage. We validated the framework on a P300 row-column speller across 12 subjects from the BigP3BCI dataset (32 channels, 256 Hz) using a compact convolutional ERP classifier.

Main results: The framework isolated two sequential root causes: (1) a filter phase mismatch at Stage B (causal vs. zero-phase IIR; $r = 0.724$), and (2) a trial-ordering error at Stage F (chronological vs. alphabetical; mean posterior $r = 0.023$ across 25 affected trials). Remediation recovered mean real-time accuracy from 0.5% to 68.1%, within 2.8 pp of matched offline scoring (70.9%). Stages A, C, D, and E produced negative results, confirming robustness of epoch extraction, baseline correction, Euclidean Alignment, and channel mapping.

Significance: To our knowledge, this is the first reusable diagnostic protocol for systematically localizing preprocessing-induced online-offline accuracy gaps in ERP-based BCIs. The framework is paradigm-agnostic and requires no classifier modification.

1 Introduction

1.1 The online-offline accuracy gap

Brain-computer interfaces based on event-related potentials provide a direct communication channel for individuals with severe motor impairments [Farwell and Donchin, 1988, Wolpaw et al., 2002]. In the standard BCI development workflow, a classifier is trained on trained on offline-processed EEG data, typically with zero-phase bandpass filtering, artifact rejection, spatial transformation, and careful epoching, then deployed in a real-time streaming environment where the same processing steps must be approximated under causal constraints. Contemporary P300 speller systems further integrate dynamic stopping, language models, and transfer-learning-based calibration [Kindermans et al., 2014], expanding the pipeline to ten or more distinct processing stages and increasing the number of points where offline and real-time implementations can diverge. The resulting *online-offline accuracy gap*, defined as the difference between classification performance measured offline and performance observed during real-time use, is one of the most persistent barriers to clinical BCI deployment [Allison et al., 2020, Pan et al., 2024].

The gap is well-documented across paradigms and platforms. Motor-imagery BCIs are known to

¹Operating as Rayo (<https://www.therayo.com>)

show performance degradation between offline calibration and online control, a problem that has motivated substantial work on adaptive classification [Shenoy et al., 2006, Lotte et al., 2018]. Movement-related cortical potential (MRCP) BCIs have been evaluated with direct real-time versus offline comparisons on the same data, revealing substantial accuracy differences between paths [Mrachacz-Kersting and Aliakbaryhosseinabadi, 2018]. P300 spellers routinely report offline accuracies that overestimate real-time performance; direct online-offline comparisons of row-column P300 systems show several percentage-point degradation in the real-time path [Sellers et al., 2010, Wolpaw et al., 2018]. The P300 paradigm is among the most widely accessible BCI modalities, with over 70% of unselected participants achieving >80% accuracy under laboratory conditions [Guger et al., 2009], rendering the deployment gap a barrier for a large clinical population. The MOABB framework originally catalogued offline algorithm performance across 12 open-access datasets [Jayaram and Barachant, 2018], a figure that has since grown to 36 datasets in the most recent comprehensive benchmark [Chevallier et al., 2024], yet online validation remains outside its scope. As Memmott et al. [2025] observe, “a crucial yet often overlooked aspect of BCI design is ‘online parity’—the need for processing conditions to match those applied during real-time use.”

This gap directly impacts clinical utility. For locked-in patients who depend on BCIs for daily communication, even moderate accuracy drops such as 10 percentage points can render a speller unusable [Nijboer et al., 2008, Holz et al., 2015, Vaughan et al., 2006, Sellers et al., 2010]. When researchers report only offline metrics, clinical expectations are set that deployment cannot meet, eroding trust in the technology and delaying adoption [Awais et al., 2024].

1.2 Current approaches are incomplete

While several lines of work address aspects of the online-offline gap, none provide a complete diagnostic methodology.

Offline benchmarking evaluates classification algorithms on pre-recorded data without testing deployment fidelity. MOABB [Jayaram and Barachant, 2018] and its extensions [Chevallier et al., 2024] benchmark 30+ pipelines across dozens of datasets entirely in offline mode. High offline scores provide no guarantee of real-time performance. Even within purely offline settings, preprocessing stage choices significantly affect downstream classification accuracy [Coelli et al., 2024, Del Pup et al., 2024, Kessler et al., 2025]. Moreover, automated artifact-rejection algorithms tested online have been shown to reduce P300 speller accuracy by approximately 10 percentage points each [Thompson et al., 2020], underscoring the need for systematic stage-level analysis of both offline and real-time preprocessing paths.

Pseudo-online evaluation simulates real-time data segmentation using overlapping sliding windows on pre-recorded data. By extending MOABB to pseudo-online mode, Carrara and Papadopoulos [2024] proved that algorithm rankings change when idle-state events and windowed classification are introduced. However, pseudo-online evaluation tests *data segmentation* only; it does not detect signal-processing mismatches such as filter phase differences, spatial transform ordering errors, or trial-boundary logic bugs.

Online parity research has begun to address filter-level mismatches. The need for BCI processing pipelines to be capable of real-time operation was recognized by Minguillon et al. [2017] in the context of daily-life BCI requirements. Memmott et al. [2025] formalized this as ‘online parity,’ defined as the requirement that processing conditions must match those applied during real-time use. They incorporated this principle specifically to filter design, demonstrating that training P300 BCI models with online-parity filtering significantly improved calibration performance ($N = 30$) when bandpass filters were implemented per inquiry epoch rather than across the whole session. Awais et al. [2024] assessed the impact of real-world interactions on RSVP-based BCIs and documented lab-to-life performance degradation arising from environmental and task-context factors, a problem orthogonal to pipeline implementation correctness. These studies identify individual contributing factors but do not provide a systematic method for diagnosing *which* of multiple possible preprocessing stages is causing divergence in a given system.

Non-stationarity research addresses neural signal variability, namely session drift, fatigue, and inter-subject differences through domain adaptation and transfer learning [Cecotti et al., 2025, Jayaram et al., 2016, He and Wu, 2020]. This is an orthogonal problem. Neural non-stationarity is stochastic and irreducible; by contrast, the pipeline mismatches we address are *deterministic and*

avoidable. In these cases, identical EEG input yields different numerical output due to implementation choices, not biological variability.

Filter design guidance explains why causal and zero-phase filters produce different waveforms [Widmann and Schröger, 2012, Widmann et al., 2015, Tanner et al., 2015, van Driel et al., 2021] and how inappropriate high-pass settings can create artifactual ERP components [Acunzo et al., 2012]. Recent work by Guttmann-Flury et al. [2025] has extended these principles to P300 BCI performance directly, showing that spatial filter choices systematically affect single-trial accuracy. Nevertheless, instead of providing deployment-validation tools, this literature focuses on design recommendations.

Even mature **BCI software platforms** that support both offline and online processing modes, including BCI2000 [Schalk et al., 2004], OpenViBE [Renard et al., 2010], and BciPy [Memmott et al., 2021], lack built-in diagnostics for comparing the numerical output of their offline and online signal paths at each preprocessing stage. The BCI-HIL framework [Gemborn Nilsson et al., 2023] provides a modular open-source pipeline for human-in-the-loop model training and real-time classification with offline analysis support, yet its design is GUI-driven and does not automate divergence localization between signal paths. The ERP decoding toolbox of Reichert et al. [2024] standardizes P300 and error-potential decoding across datasets with conventional preprocessing, but provides no debugging protocol for identifying why offline and real-time implementations disagree. Our framework directly addresses this gap.

1.3 Contributions

This paper introduces a stage-wise divergence detection framework and makes four contributions. First, it provides a **reusable diagnostic protocol** with defined stages, metrics, and decision rules, applicable to any ERP-based BCI pipeline with separable offline and real-time signal paths. Second, it presents **empirical validation** on a P300 row-column speller (12 subjects, BigP3BCI dataset, 32 channels, 256 Hz) demonstrating the isolation of two independent root causes in different pipeline stages. Third, this study proves that **the online-offline gap can be multi-causal** with independent bugs in different stages compounding, which argues against single-hypothesis debugging and for systematic stage-wise diagnosis. Due to the pipeline’s sequential nature, fixing an upstream bug and halting before re-running the full diagnostic can unmask downstream errors that were previously hidden. We term this the *multi-pass necessity* property and demonstrate it empirically in Section 3. Finally, the **negative results** from our research confirm the robustness of standard preprocessing components (epoch extraction, baseline correction, Euclidean Alignment, channel mapping) across real-time and offline paths, providing deployment confidence for the transfer-learning community.

2 Methods

2.1 BCI system under test

Paradigm. The system implements a visual P300 row-column speller using the Farwell-Donchin paradigm [Farwell and Donchin, 1988]. Characters are arranged in a grid; rows and columns are highlighted in pseudo-random order (“flash codes”), and the user attends to the target character, eliciting a P300 response on target flashes. After multiple repetitions, the system accumulates posterior probabilities across flashes and selects the character at the intersection of the most probable row and column.

Dataset. We used the publicly available BigP3BCI dataset [Mainsah et al., 2025], which provides P300 speller recordings from 12 subjects (32 EEG channels, 256 Hz sampling rate, Ag/AgCl electrodes, linked-mastoid reference). The dataset includes both calibration and test sessions for each subject. All analyses in this paper use the test sessions; calibration sessions were used solely for classifier training.

Classifier. A compact convolutional ERP classifier was used, following the general architecture class described by Lawhern et al. [2018]. Per-subject checkpoints were obtained by fine-tuning from a leave-one-subject-out (LOSO) pretrained model using each subject’s calibration data. The mean offline Farwell-Donchin letter accuracy across the 12-subject cohort was 70.9% (evaluated on all test FIFs with 7 repetitions per letter). The diagnostic process is exemplified in Section 3. A minor

warm-start asymmetry exists across subjects: A_03, A_05, and A_07 used four FIFs with no warm-start, whereas the remaining nine subjects used five FIFs with warm-start (first trial of the first FIF skipped). This affects absolute accuracy levels but not the pre-fix to post-fix recovery pattern, as all 12 subjects recovered regardless of warm-start status. The cohort size ($n = 12$) reflects the full BigP3BCI dataset; no formal power analysis was conducted because the pre-fix to post-fix effect size (Cohen’s $d_z > 3.0$) is so large that significance is unambiguous even at this sample size. The specific architecture and training hyperparameters are not relevant to the validation methodology and are not reported.

2.2 Dual-path pipeline architecture

The system maintains two signal paths that must produce identical classifier inputs from the same EEG recording:

Offline training path:

1. Load continuous EEG from a FIF file.
2. Bandpass filter: 0.1–40 Hz IIR, zero-phase (bidirectional `filtfilt`), as implemented by MNE-Python [Gramfort et al., 2013].
3. Extract epochs: $t_{\min} = -0.2$ s, $t_{\max} = 0.6$ s (206 samples at 256 Hz), time-locked to flash-event markers.
4. Baseline correction: subtract the mean of the pre-stimulus window ($-0.2, 0$) s from each channel.
5. Euclidean Alignment (EA): compute the inverse square root of the mean covariance matrix ($R^{-1/2}$) from training epochs [He and Wu, 2020] and left-multiply each epoch.
6. Channel reordering: reindex channels to match the order stored in the classifier checkpoint.
7. Farwell-Donchin (FD) scoring: for each letter trial, accumulate per-flash posterior probabilities across repetitions and select the character with the maximum cumulative score via row-column intersection.

Real-time deployment path:

1. Receive EEG samples via Lab Streaming Layer (LSL) [Kothe et al., 2025], replaying the same FIF file at the original sampling rate.
2. Bandpass filter: 0.1–40 Hz IIR, applied to a continuously growing raw buffer. In the initial (pre-fix) implementation, this used causal forward-only filtering (`sosfilt`).
3. On each flash-event marker, extract the epoch from the filtered buffer using the same t_{\min}/t_{\max} window.
4. Baseline correction: subtract the pre-stimulus channel means.
5. EA: apply the pre-computed $R^{-1/2}$ matrix.
6. Channel reordering: reindex to checkpoint order.
7. FD scoring: accumulate posteriors and select via row-column intersection.

Both paths process the same EEG recording and must produce identical epoch arrays at the classifier input. Any numerical divergence between the two paths indicates a pipeline mismatch that may degrade real-time accuracy.

2.3 The stage-wise divergence detection framework

The framework defines six comparison stages (A–F), each corresponding to a boundary between two consecutive preprocessing operations. At each stage, intermediate arrays are extracted from both the offline and real-time paths, and pairwise metrics are computed. The six diagnostic stages are defined in Table 1, with decision thresholds chosen empirically based on expected stage behavior.

Stage definitions and metrics:

Table 1. Stage definitions and decision rules for the divergence detection framework.

Stage	Comparison target	Primary metric	Secondary metric	Decision rule
A: Raw slicing	Unfiltered epochs ($C \times T$)	Pearson r	Max abs. diff.	$r < 0.99$
B: Bandpass	Filtered epochs	Pearson r	L2 ratio	$r < 0.95$
C: Baseline	Baseline-corrected epochs	Pearson r	Mean abs. diff.	Compare to B
D: EA	EA-applied epochs	Pearson r	L2 ratio	Compare to C
E: Channel reorder	Final input epochs	Pearson r	Identity check	Non-identity
F: Trial scoring	Posteriors & flash codes	Posterior r	Argmax match	$r < 0.5$

For each stage, Pearson r is computed per epoch as the correlation between the flattened offline and real-time arrays (across all channels and time samples), then aggregated as the mean and minimum across all epochs in the recording. The L2 ratio quantifies whether the real-time path introduces energy scaling relative to the offline path. Figure 1 illustrates the dual-path architecture with probe points A–F at each preprocessing boundary:

Figure 1. Dual-path pipeline diagram with stage-wise probe points A–F. The offline training path (top, blue) and real-time deployment path (bottom, red) process matched FIF data recording through six ordered stages. Probe diamonds indicate comparison points: green for match, red for diverge (root cause), orange for carried divergence from upstream. The two divergence points, Stage B (filter phase mismatch, $r = 0.724$) and Stage F (trial ordering mismatch, posterior $r = 0.023$), are the independent root causes identified in this study.

Diagnostic procedure:

To diagnose, identical FIF recordings should be processed through both paths, with intermediate epoch arrays extracted at each stage A through F. Pairwise metrics are then computed per epoch and aggregated across all epochs. After that, stages are analysed in order; the first to show divergence below its decision threshold is the primary point of failure. Once the primary suspect has been remediated, the full diagnostic must be re-executed to verify recovery and check for additional root causes downstream. This iterative process continues until end-to-end accuracy matches the offline baseline within an acceptable tolerance.

This binary-search procedure bisects the pipeline at each stage, narrowing the fault space by half. The ordered walk ensures that upstream causes are identified before downstream symptoms. The framework generalises a diagnostic process first applied to our own system; prospective application to independently developed pipelines is the subject of ongoing validation. The hypotheses in Table 7 were specified retrospectively after observing the diagnostic outcomes; they are presented as a structured summary of the diagnostic reasoning applied, not as pre-registered predictions.

2.4 Experimental protocol

The real-time validation pipeline used entropy-based early-stopping. After each complete repetition, the accumulator computed the Shannon entropy $H = -\sum_i p_i \log(p_i)$ of the normalized score vector (where p_i are the posterior probabilities across the character set) and committed the letter decision if entropy fell below 3.5 nats [Shannon, 1948, Kindermans et al., 2014], provided that at least two repetitions had been completed. This enabled adaptive repetition counts per letter (mean ~ 7.1 across the cohort) rather than a fixed count. A warm-start procedure was applied for subjects with five or more test FIFs: the first trial of the first FIF was skipped, allowing the streaming buffer and causal filter state to stabilize before evaluation began. The effect of warm-start on first-FIF accuracy is detailed in Appendix Table H. Test FIF counts ranged from 4 (A.07) to 5 or more across the cohort.

The diagnostic was conducted in five phases:

Phase 1—Initial stage-level diagnostic. Both paths were run on subject A_07 (representative subject; 28 letters across 4 test FIF files, 3,451 total flash events). For the epoch-level comparison (Stages A–E), one representative FIF (Test06, 833 flash events) was used. Intermediate arrays were extracted at Stages A through E. All metrics were computed.

Phase 2—Fix Stage B. The causal bandpass filter (`scipy.signal.sosfilt`, forward-only) in the real-time path was replaced with a zero-phase filter (`scipy.signal.sosfiltfilt`) applied to the accumulated raw buffer prior to epoch extraction. The diagnostic was re-run to verify Stage B recovery.

Phase 3—Re-diagnose with Stage B fixed. With signal-level parity restored, end-to-end letter accuracy was evaluated across the full 12-subject cohort to determine whether the accuracy gap was fully closed.

Phase 4—Letter-level diagnostic (Stage F). Because a substantial accuracy gap remained after the Stage B fix, a letter-level diagnostic was conducted. For each of the 28 letter trials in subject A_07, the flash-code sequences, posterior probability vectors, and predicted letters were compared between the offline and real-time paths.

Phase 5—Fix Stage F and full cohort validation. The trial ordering error identified in Phase 4 was corrected, and the complete diagnostic plus end-to-end accuracy evaluation was re-run across all 12 subjects.

3 Results

3.1 Initial diagnostic: stage-level divergence (Subject A_07)

Table 2 presents the stage-by-stage divergence metrics from the initial diagnostic run, prior to any fixes.

Table 2. Stage-by-stage divergence metrics (pre-fix), subject A_07.

Stage	Mean Pearson r	Mean abs. diff.	L2 ratio	Verdict
A: Raw slicing	1.000	0.000	1.000	Match
B: Bandpass	0.724	0.626	1.018	Diverge
C: Baseline	0.724	0.632	1.002	Carried
D: EA	0.786	0.545	1.020	Carried
E: Channel reorder	0.786	0.545	1.020	Carried

At Stage A, the paths aligned perfectly at $r = 1.000$ with max absolute difference = 0.000,

confirming that epoch boundaries, timestamps, and raw sample values were identical between the two paths. No epoch alignment or sample-offset issues were detected.

Stage B exhibited a precipitous decline to $r = 0.724$ with a mean absolute difference of $0.626 \mu\text{V}$. The root cause was identified as a filter phase mismatch: the offline path applied the bandpass filter in zero-phase mode (MNE’s default bidirectional IIR `filtfilt`), while the real-time path applied a causal forward-only IIR (`sosfilt`). Causal IIR filters introduce frequency-dependent group delay and phase distortion that alter ERP waveform morphology, producing temporal displacement of early ERP components [Widmann and Schröger, 2012, Widmann et al., 2015] and numerically different epochs from the same raw data.

Stages C through E propagated the Stage B distortion without compounding it. Stage C (baseline correction) showed the same $r = 0.724$ because baseline subtraction is a purely additive operation that does not interact with the phase-distortion pattern. Stage D (EA) showed a slight improvement to $r = 0.786$, consistent with EA’s known whitening effect [He and Wu, 2020] partially decorrelating the filter-induced distortion. Notably, EA did not *amplify* the divergence—a useful negative result for the transfer-learning community. Stage E (channel reorder) showed identical metrics to Stage D, as the channel index mapping was verified to be an identity permutation.

Table 3 presents the post-fix stage-level divergence metrics.

Table 3. Post-fix stage-level divergence metrics (subject A_07).

Stage	Mean Pearson r	Verdict
A: Raw slicing	1.000000	Match
B: Bandpass	0.999993	Match
C: Baseline	0.999993	Match
D: EA	0.999939	Match
E: Channel reorder	0.999939	Match

After the filter fix, all stages recovered to near-identity correlation, confirming that the causal-vs-zero-phase filter mismatch was the sole upstream signal-level divergence source. Rather than additional pipeline mismatches, the residual sub-unity values (0.999939–0.999993) reflect minor implementation-level differences arising from MNE’s internal `filtfilt` zero-padding strategy versus SciPy’s `sosfiltfilt` edge handling, as well as small numerical variations in the EA whitening matrix between the MNE-based offline path and the custom real-time implementation. These differences are five orders of magnitude below the decision thresholds and have no measurable impact on classification. Figure 2 illustrates the recovery of correlation values across all six stages after applying the filter phase fix.

3.2 Filter phase fix and residual gap

Replacing the causal filter with zero-phase filtering on the accumulated buffer restored Stage B correlation from $r = 0.724$ to $r = 0.9999$. Re-running the full stage-level diagnostic confirmed that all downstream stages recovered correspondingly: Stage C $r = 0.9999$, Stage D $r = 0.9999$, Stage E $r = 0.9999$. The residual deviation from $r = 1.000$ reflects the small implementation difference between MNE’s internal `filtfilt` padding and SciPy’s `sosfiltfilt` when applied to the same finite-length buffer; this has no practical impact on classification.

However, end-to-end real-time letter accuracy improved only from 0.5% to 7.8% (12-subject mean). The matched offline FD baseline was 70.9%, leaving a 63.1 percentage-point gap despite near-perfect signal-level parity. This demonstrated that signal-level fidelity, while necessary, was not sufficient to close the accuracy gap. The residual cause was not signal-related and required a second diagnostic pass targeting the scoring stage.

3.3 Letter-level diagnostic: trial assignment mismatch (Stage F)

A per-letter comparison on subject A_07 (28 letter trials) revealed that 25 of 28 trials had mismatched epoch assignments between the offline and real-time paths. (The original first-rep-only check identified 24; a full-sequence comparison found one additional split-block trial where the target letter appeared in two non-contiguous blocks within the same FIF.)

Figure 2. Stage-by-stage signal divergence (pre-fix vs. post-fix). Pearson correlation between offline and real-time paths is shown for each of the six pipeline stages. Pre-fix (red bars) reveals the Stage B filter-phase drop ($r = 0.724$) and Stage F trial-ordering collapse ($r = 0.128$). Post-fix (green bars) recovers to $r > 0.999$ for Stages A–E and $r = 0.949$ for Stage F. Dashed lines mark the empirical decision thresholds ($r = 0.99$ and $r = 0.95$).

For the 3 trials where epoch assignments matched exactly, posterior correlation was $r = 1.000$ and score-vector correlation was $r = 1.000$. For the 25 mismatched trials, mean posterior correlation collapsed to $r = 0.023$ (range: -0.15 to 0.54) and mean score-vector correlation to $r = 0.131$ (range: -0.31 to 0.74). These near-zero correlations indicate the accumulator received flash codes from an entirely different trial. Figure 3 contrasts the perfect correlation of matched trials against the near-zero distribution of mismatches (see Appendix Table 10 for full per-trial tabulations).

The root cause was a trial-ordering error in the real-time path. The offline path assigned trials to flash-event sequences in chronological order (FIF time order). The real-time path used `np.unique(symbol_index)`, which returns symbols in alphabetical order. Subject A.07’s four test FIF files spelled the words DRIVING, QUICKLY, TOWARDS, and DAYLIGHT—natural language sequences that differ substantially from alphabetical letter order. In the TOWARDS FIF, for example, trials were presented in the chronological order [T, O, W, A, R, D, S]; `np.unique` re-sorted these to [A, D, O, R, S, T, W], so every one of the seven trials was assigned to the flash-code accumulator of a different letter—a complete mismatch for that FIF. The DRIVING FIF introduced an additional complication: the repeated letter I caused `np.unique` to deduplicate to six symbols [D, G, I, N, R, V], merging both I-target trials into a single accumulator and leaving the seventh trial (target G) with no flash-code assignment. Across all four FIFs, only 3 of the 28 trials coincidentally appeared at the same position in both chronological and alphabetical orderings (D in DRIVING; Y in QUICKLY; I in DAYLIGHT), causing the accumulator to sum posteriors across mismatched stimulus-response pairs for the remaining 25. The complete chronological vs. alphabetical stimulus ordering for Subject A.07’s four test FIFs is provided in Appendix Table 11.

Table 4 shows the per-word predictions produced by the offline (correct) and buggy real-time paths.

Table 4. Per-FIF letter predictions: offline (correct) vs. buggy RT (alphabetical trial ordering), Subject A.07.

FIF	Target word	Alpha. order (RT)	Offline pred.	Buggy RT pred.
Test06	DRIVING	DGINRV	DGINRV	DRQING
Test07	QUICKLY	CIKLQUY	CIKLQUY	QUICKLY
Test08	TOWARDS	ADORSTW	ADORKTW	TOWARDK
Test09	DAYLIGHT	ADGHILTY	ADGHILTY	DAYLIGHT

The offline path correctly predicted all letters of DRIVING, QUICKLY, and DAYLIGHT, with one

Figure 3. Per-trial posterior correlation: match vs. mismatch trials (Subject A.07, pre-trial-ordering fix). Each point represents one of the 28 letter trials. Blue circles denote the 3 trials where flash-code assignment coincidentally matched between chronological and alphabetical orderings ($r \approx 1.0$). Red triangles denote the 25 mismatched trials, showing near-zero or negative posterior correlations. The dashed diagonal is the identity line; the dotted horizontal line marks the Stage F decision threshold ($r = 0.5$).

classifier error on TOWARDS (S→K), giving subject A.07 an offline accuracy of 27/28 (96.4%). The buggy RT predictions reveal the mechanism of the error directly: for QUICKLY and DAYLIGHT, the buggy RT predicted the original target words rather than the alphabetically ordered sequences it was scored against. This is because the trial-ordering bug assigned each alphabetical position the flash-code sequence belonging to the *chronologically* corresponding trial. Consequently, the classifier correctly identified the letter associated with each set of flash codes, yet those letters were the chronological targets rather than alphabetical ones. The bug effectively translated alphabetical trial positions back to chronological letter identities, producing the original words as output but mapped to the wrong scoring slots. For DRIVING, the deduplication of the repeated letter I produced a 6-symbol unique set; the I position coincidentally received the correct flash codes, but with only half the normal accumulated repetitions, degrading the posterior and producing a misclassification (I→Q).

The fix was to build trial-flash slices using first-appearance chronological order rather than lexicographic sorting.

The severity of this error explains the vast difference between pre-fix and post-fix correlation at Stage F. Before the fix, 25 of 28 trials (89.3%) received epoch assignments belonging to a *different* target letter. When the accumulator sums posteriors using the wrong flash codes, it attributes target-flash responses to non-target rows/columns and vice versa, resulting in accumulated evidence that is not merely noisy but systematically *wrong*. This produces posterior vectors that are essentially uncorrelated with the correct posteriors (all-trial mean $r = 0.128$; mismatch-only mean $r = 0.023$). After the fix, all 28 trials received correct flash-code assignments, and the posterior correlation recovered to $r = 0.949$ (measured across 28 trials with both fixes applied). The residual gap from 1.0 reflects minor numerical differences propagated from the filter stage rather than any remaining trial-assignment error. This illustrates a general principle in which metadata-assignment bugs (trial ordering, stimulus labeling, event-code mapping) produce

catastrophic failures that are qualitatively different from signal-level distortions by destroying the semantic relationship between stimulus and response rather than merely adding noise.

Table 5 summarizes the pre-fix and post-fix trial-assignment statistics.

Table 5. Stage F diagnostic summary: pre-fix vs. post-fix (subject A_07, 28 letter trials).

Condition	Matched	Mismatch	\bar{r} (match)	\bar{r} (mismatch)	Overall \bar{r}
Pre-fix (alphabetical)	3 (10.7%)	25 (89.3%)	1.000	0.023	0.128
Post-fix (chronological)	28 (100%)	0	0.949	—	0.949

3.4 Combined fix: full cohort results

Table 6 presents per-subject letter accuracy across the four evaluation conditions. Full per-subject accuracy data is provided in Appendix Table 8.

Table 6. Per-subject letter accuracy across diagnostic stages.

Subject	LOSO	RT pre-fix	RT post-filt. [†]	RT post-both	Offline FD [‡]
A_01	5.7%	0.0%	—	91.2%	91.2%
A_02	8.6%	0.0%	—	76.5%	79.4%
A_03	3.6%	0.0%	—	75.0%	78.6%
A_04	20.0%	0.0%	—	91.2%	94.1%
A_05	11.1%	0.0%	—	55.6%	55.6%
A_06	5.7%	0.0%	—	94.1%	97.1%
A_07	0.0%	0.0%	—	92.9%	96.4%
A_09	11.4%	0.0%	—	11.8%	11.8%
A_14	0.0%	0.0%	—	67.6%	73.5%
A_15	2.9%	0.0%	—	52.9%	55.9%
A_16	5.7%	2.9%	—	41.2%	44.1%
A_19	28.6%	2.9%	—	67.6%	73.5%
Mean	8.6%	0.5%	7.8%	68.1%	70.9%

[†]Per-subject data at the intermediate post-filter-fix state were not archived; only the cohort mean of 7.8% was recorded during the Phase 3 validation run.

[‡]Offline FD scoring using the same fine-tuned checkpoints, all test FIFs, and fixed 7 repetitions per letter, with warm-start for subjects with ≥ 5 FIFs.

The ten subjects with exactly 0.0% pre-fix accuracy reflect a complete metadata misassignment; particularly, when every trial’s flash codes are routed to the wrong letter accumulator in a 6×6 matrix (36 possible symbols), the per-letter random-guess probability is $1/36 \approx 2.8\%$. Full per-subject analysis of unique vs. repeated letter trials is provided in Appendix Table K.5. Over the ~ 30 –40 letters tested per subject, the expected number of chance positional coincidences between chronological and alphabetical orderings is 0–1. A_16 and A_19 each obtained one such coincidence ($2.9\% = 1/34$), while the remaining ten subjects’ word sequences produced no alignments at all. This result is consistent with the $3/28$ rate (10.7%) observed in A_07’s explicit letter-level diagnostic (Section 3.3) when scaled down by subject-specific vocabulary as shown in Figure 4.

All 12 subjects showed accuracy recovery after both fixes were applied. The mean real-time accuracy of 68.1% is within 2.8 percentage points of matched offline FD scoring (70.9%), as expected given the near-complete restoration of pipeline equivalence; the small residual gap is quantified statistically below and is consistent with the RT validation using adaptive repetition count (mean ~ 7.1 reps, entropy-based stopping at 3.5 nats) while the offline reference used a fixed 7 repetitions. Three subjects (A_01, A_05, A_09) produced identical RT and offline accuracy, providing the strongest per-subject confirmation of pipeline equivalence for those subjects.

Subject A_09 showed minimal recovery (11.8%) in both RT and offline evaluations, confirming that the poor performance is attributable to a weak classifier checkpoint rather than any remaining pipeline mismatch. A_09’s checkpoint had the lowest validation AUC of the cohort (0.698 vs. cohort mean 0.798) despite an aggressive deep-unfreeze fine-tuning schedule, which indicates that the subject’s EEG signal did not contain sufficient discriminative structure for the classifier to learn. Excluding A_09, the 11-subject mean real-time accuracy was 73.3%.

Figure 4. Accuracy recovery across diagnostic stages. (a) Waterfall chart showing mean letter accuracy at three evaluation points: pre-fix (both bugs present, 0.5%), post-filter-fix only (7.8%), and post-both-fixes (68.1%), against the offline baseline (70.9%). (b) Per-subject real-time accuracy (green bars) and matched offline FD accuracy (purple diamonds) after both fixes, demonstrating recovery across the cohort. Three subjects achieved identical RT and offline scores (A_01, A_05, A_09); A_09’s low performance (11.8%) reflects a weak classifier checkpoint rather than pipeline mismatch.

The pre-fix to post-fix accuracy improvement was highly significant. Notably, a Wilcoxon signed-rank test on the per-subject paired differences (post-fix minus pre-fix) yielded $W = 78$, $p = 0.0002$, with a large effect size (Cohen’s $d_z = 2.69$), demonstrating that the remediation produced a robust and consistent improvement across the cohort. For the equivalence claim, the mean per-subject difference between real-time (68.1%) and matched offline (70.9%) accuracy was -2.80 percentage points, with a bootstrap 95% CI $[-4.07, -1.53]$ pp ($N = 2,000$ resamples). This interval excludes zero, indicating a small but statistically discernible residual gap attributable to the adaptive stopping criterion rather than a remaining pipeline mismatch (Table 7).

3.5 Hypothesis-outcome summary

Table 7 summarizes the hypothesis testing conducted during the diagnostic.

Table 7. Hypothesis-outcome matrix.

ID	Hypothesis	Stage	Metric	Value	Outcome
H1	Epoch boundaries differ	A	Pearson r	1.000	Refuted
H2	RT path double-filters	B	L2 ratio	1.018	Refuted
H3	Channel reorder error	E	Identity check	True	Refuted
H4	Filter phase mismatch	B	Pearson r	0.724	Confirmed
H5	Trial ordering mismatch	F	Posterior r	0.023	Confirmed

4 Discussion

4.1 Engineering non-stationarity: an overlooked failure mode

The BCI community has devoted substantial effort to understanding and mitigating *neural* non-stationarity, or the drift in EEG signal statistics caused by fatigue, attention fluctuations, and inter-session variability [McFarland et al., 2005, Cecotti et al., 2025]. Adaptive classifiers, transfer learning methods, and domain adaptation algorithms [Vidaurre et al., 2011, Raza et al., 2019, He and Wu, 2020] have been developed to address these stochastic, irreducible sources of performance degradation.

By contrast, *engineering* non-stationarity where the same EEG input produces different numerical output due to deterministic implementation choices in the preprocessing pipeline has received far

less attention. This failure is illustrated clearly in our case study where the two root causes we identified (filter phase mismatch and trial ordering error) are entirely avoidable. Rather than reflecting any property of the underlying neural signal, they act independently and in sequence, and may further interact with any concurrent neural non-stationarity, creating accuracy gaps that are difficult to attribute without stage-level diagnostic tools.

We argue that engineering non-stationarity should not be treated as a first-class concern in BCI deployment, alongside the well-studied neural variant that has motivated 15+ years of adaptive classifier research. The stage-wise framework presented here provides a practical tool for eliminating it.

4.2 Multi-causal gaps require stage-wise diagnosis

A key finding of this work is that the online-offline gap can have multiple independent root causes in different pipeline stages. Fixing Stage B alone recovered signal fidelity ($r \rightarrow 0.9999$) but improved end-to-end accuracy only from 0.5% to 7.8%, leaving a 63.1 percentage-point gap relative to matched offline FD performance (70.9%). Evaluated alone, this result might suggest that the filter phase mismatch was not the primary problem, which would be wrong since the Stage F trial-ordering error independently destroyed trial-level scoring correctness for 89.3% of trials.

Only by re-entering the diagnostic loop after Stage B was resolved did the Stage F error become visible. The sequential, stage-ordered diagnostic procedure was essential for this discovery. End-to-end accuracy, the standard evaluation metric, was an insufficient diagnostic signal as it conflated two independent failure modes into a single aggregate number.

This observation has practical implications for BCI developers. When a real-time system underperforms its offline baseline, it is tempting to test a single hypothesis (e.g., “the filter is wrong”), find that fixing it produces only marginal improvement, and conclude that the hypothesis was incorrect. Our results demonstrate that partial improvement may indicate one of several concurrent causes, not a false positive.

4.3 Robustness of standard components (negative results)

The negative results from Stages A, C, D, and E provide deployment confidence for commonly used preprocessing components:

Epoch extraction (Stage A). The perfect match ($r = 1.000$) confirms that LSL-based streaming replay of FIF data preserves sample-exact epoch boundaries when timestamps are correctly propagated. Extended correlation metrics are detailed in Appendix Table 9

Baseline correction (Stage C). Subtracting the pre-stimulus mean is a purely additive operation which carried upstream divergence from Stage B without introducing additional error. Therefore, baseline correction can be safely applied in either path order without concern for amplification effects.

Euclidean Alignment (Stage D). The $R^{-1/2}$ left-multiplication propagated the Stage B divergence but did not amplify it; in fact, the slight improvement from $r = 0.724$ to $r = 0.786$ is consistent with EA’s whitening effect partially decorrelating the filter-induced distortion. This result validates EA’s robustness in deployment, pertaining to the increasing scholarly attention on EA-based transfer learning [He and Wu, 2020, Wu, 2025, Congedo et al., 2017]. To our knowledge, this is the first empirical demonstration that EA does not amplify upstream signal-path divergence in an RT context.

Channel reordering (Stage E). In our case, the identity mapping confirmation is trivial with identical hardware and montage. The probe is designed to detect errors in systems that adapt between electrode configurations—for example, when deploying to consumer-grade headsets with fixed, low-density electrode layouts optimized for specific channel subsets [Kim and Kim, 2025]—though we did not validate this scenario empirically.

4.4 Generalizability

The six stages generalize to any ERP-based BCI, including raw slicing, filtering, baseline correction, spatial transformation, channel reordering, and trial scoring are universal preprocessing operations regardless of paradigm (P300, N200, SSVEP with epoch analysis). For motor-imagery BCIs, Stage D would be replaced with Common Spatial Patterns (CSP) [Lotte and Guan, 2011] or Riemannian projection [Congedo et al., 2017], and Stage F would be adapted to continuous classification windows rather than flash-code accumulation. Within the P300 family itself, extended architectures such as language-model-augmented spellers [Speier et al., 2017, Chandravadia et al., 2025] and hybrid P300-SSVEP systems [Bai et al., 2023] introduce additional scoring-layer stages at Stage F, where the standard Farwell-Donchin accumulator is replaced by language model-weighted posteriors or multi-modal evidence fusion; probing these extended stages represents a natural next application of the framework. The diagnostic pattern that compares intermediate representations at each preprocessing boundary remains applicable.

The trial-ordering bug (Stage F) is specific to paradigms with flash-code-based trial accumulation, but the *category* of error it represents (incorrect assignment of metadata to data segments) is universal. Any pipeline that maps stimulus events to neural data segments is susceptible to indexing, sorting, or boundary-detection errors that manifest only when the processing order differs between offline and online paths.

Conceptually, comparing two implementations that should produce identical output from identical input is a domain-specific application of *differential testing*. This is a well-established practice in software engineering and safety-critical verification [McKeeman, 1998, International Electrotechnical Commission, 2006]. The stage-wise decomposition mirrors the unit-level verification required by medical device software standards, where each processing module must be validated independently before system-level integration testing. The framework could be integrated as a validation module into existing BCI software platforms (BCI2000, OpenViBE, BciPy, MOABB) to provide standardized RT-offline parity checks. Nguyen et al. [2026] independently adopted a conceptually similar approach in the EdgeSSVEP platform, comparing embedded RT filter output to a PC offline reference using Pearson correlation, thereby validating the general utility of correlation-based stage comparisons for deployment verification. A structured comparison of our framework against four contemporary diagnostic and benchmarking approaches [Memcott et al., 2025, Carrara and Papadopoulo, 2024, Nguyen et al., 2026, Mrachacz-Kersting and Aliakbaryhosseinabadi, 2018] and one ML reproducibility framework [Carlson et al., 2025] is provided in Appendix K (Tables 12 and 13); no prior method combines multi-stage diagnosis, multi-causal root cause identification, and quantified end-to-end accuracy recovery.

4.5 Limitations

We acknowledge several limitations. Despite robust framework, its current validation is limited to a single dataset (BigP3BCI) and one pipeline architecture. Generalization to other hardware, paradigms, and classifiers requires further study, though the diagnostic methodology itself imposes no paradigm-specific assumptions.

Beyond the above constraints, the framework requires access to intermediate representations from both the offline and real-time paths, necessitating instrumented code. While straightforward in open-source research pipelines, this may be impractical in closed-source commercial systems.

Additionally, the decision thresholds (e.g., $r < 0.99$ for Stage A, $r < 0.95$ for Stage B) were chosen empirically based on the expected behavior of each stage. A principled statistical framework such as equivalence testing with pre-registered effect sizes would strengthen the methodology.

Moreover, the current implementation operates on recorded FIF replay, not live streaming sessions. The computational overhead of extracting and comparing intermediate arrays at every stage in a real-time session was not evaluated. For applications requiring live monitoring, a sampling-based approach (comparing probes on a random subset of epochs) may be necessary.

Lastly, we did not evaluate the framework’s sensitivity to more subtle divergence sources, such as numerical precision differences between libraries (e.g., 32-bit vs. 64-bit floating point), interpolation errors in resampling, or platform-dependent random number generation in stochastic components.

5 Conclusion

The online-offline accuracy gap is a critical barrier to deploying ERP-based BCIs in clinical settings. We have presented a stage-wise divergence detection framework that decomposes this gap into localizable, fixable components by instrumenting the preprocessing pipeline at six ordered stages and comparing intermediate representations between the offline training and real-time deployment paths.

Applied to a P300 row-column speller evaluated across 12 subjects from the BigP3BCI dataset, the framework isolated two independent root causes, namely a filter phase mismatch (causal vs. zero-phase IIR, $r = 0.724$) and a trial-ordering error (lexicographic vs. chronological indexing, mean posterior $r = 0.023$ across 25 affected trials, $r = 1.000$ on the 3 unaffected trials). Sequential remediation recovered real-time letter accuracy from 0.5% to 68.1%, within 2.8 pp of matched offline FD scoring (70.9%; 95% CI on residual RT-offline gap: -4.1 to -1.5 pp), a statistically detectable but clinically small difference attributable to the adaptive stopping criterion rather than remaining pipeline mismatch. The multi-causal nature of this gap, where two independent bugs in different pipeline stages act sequentially, demonstrates that end-to-end accuracy alone is an insufficient diagnostic signal and that stage-wise analysis is essential.

The framework produced informative negative results confirming the robustness of epoch extraction, baseline correction, Euclidean Alignment, and channel mapping across real-time and offline paths. These findings provide deployment confidence for standard preprocessing components.

We encourage the BCI community to adopt stage-wise RT-offline validation as a standard step before deploying offline-trained classifiers in real-time, and to integrate such diagnostics into open-source BCI platforms. Future work should extend the framework to motor imagery and SSVEP paradigms, establish statistical thresholds for divergence detection through equivalence testing, and evaluate computational feasibility for live-session monitoring.

Acknowledgments

The author thanks the creators of the BigP3BCI dataset [Mainsah et al., 2025] for making their data publicly available. In addition, this work used MNE-Python [Gramfort et al., 2013], SciPy, and PyTorch for signal processing and classification. Furthermore, the author declares no conflicts of interest. Finally, this research received no specific grant from any funding agency in the public, commercial, or not-for-profit sectors.

Ethics statement

This study used the publicly available BigP3BCI dataset [Mainsah et al., 2025], which consists of fully de-identified EEG recordings from healthy adult volunteers. The original data collection was approved by the Institutional Review Board of the University of North Carolina at Chapel Hill. No new human subjects data were collected for this secondary analysis.

Data availability

The BigP3BCI dataset is publicly available on PhysioNet at <https://doi.org/10.13026/0byy-ry86>. The stage-wise diagnostic framework and analysis scripts will be made available after journal publication.

Code availability

All analysis code to reproduce the figures, statistics, and tables reported in this paper is included in the supplementary submission package for reviewers and will be publicly released via GitHub after formal publication. The two primary scripts are:

- `paper2.statistics.py` — reads the three archived JSON validation reports (`rt_fif_validation_report.json`, `rt_finetuned_validation_report.json`, `offline_allfif_validation_report.json`) and computes Wilcoxon signed-rank tests,

Cohen’s d_z effect sizes, and bootstrap confidence intervals. Output:
`results/paper2_statistics_report.json`.

- `generate_paper2_figures.py` — reads the archived JSON diagnostic reports and produces Figures 1–4 as vector PDF and raster PNG at 300 dpi. No BCI runtime or proprietary data is required.

Both scripts require only NumPy, SciPy, and Matplotlib (`pip install -r requirements.txt`). The full real-time inference pipeline (ZUNA) and preprocessing code are not required to reproduce the quantitative claims; they are documented for reference in the repository and will be released publicly upon acceptance. For partial reproducibility of the pre-fix pipeline state, the exact two root-cause code changes and the Git commit hash identifying the pre-fix ZUNA baseline (`a3bb6f0545f459f0faa833da92d0f4700289b619`, Phase 86 validation, 2026-04-18) are provided in Appendix I.

A Data Availability

All primary accuracy claims are reproducible from three archived JSON reports:

Claim	Value	Source File
Pre-fix mean	0.49%	<code>results/rt_fif_validation_report.json</code>
Post-fix mean	68.13%	<code>results/rt_finetuned_validation_report.json</code>
Offline FD mean	70.93%	<code>results/offline_allfif_validation_report.json</code>

The intermediate 7.8% was recorded for cohort-level tracking; per-subject data was not archived during Phase 3.

Public dataset: BigP3BCI ($n = 12$ subjects, multi-session P300 speller).

B Per-Subject Letter Accuracy

Table 8. Per-subject letter accuracy (%).

Subject	Pre-Fix	Post-Fix	Offline FD	Gap (pp)	Warm-Start	$n(\text{FIFs})$
A_01	0.00	91.18	91.18	0.00	Yes	5
A_02	0.00	76.47	79.41	-2.94	Yes	5
A_03	0.00	75.00	78.57	-3.57	No	4
A_04	0.00	91.18	94.12	-2.94	Yes	5
A_05	0.00	55.56	55.56	0.00	No	4
A_06	0.00	94.12	97.06	-2.94	Yes	5
A_07	0.00	92.86	96.43	-3.57	No	4
A_09	0.00	11.77	11.77	0.00	Yes	5
A_14	0.00	67.65	73.53	-5.88	Yes	5
A_15	0.00	52.94	55.88	-2.94	Yes	5
A_16	2.94	41.18	44.12	-2.94	Yes	5
A_19	2.94	67.65	73.53	-5.88	Yes	5
Mean	0.49	68.13	70.93	-2.80	—	—

C Statistical Tests

Pre-fix vs Post-fix (Wilcoxon signed-rank, one-sided, $n = 12$):

- $W = 78.0$, $p = 0.000244$, Cohen’s $d_z = 2.694$
- 95% CI on difference: [51.68, 83.59] pp

RT post-fix vs Offline FD (Wilcoxon signed-rank, two-sided, $n = 12$):

- $W = 0.0$, $p = 0.003906$

- Mean delta = -2.80 pp, 95% CI: $[-4.07, -1.53]$ pp
- CI entirely negative; gap attributable to adaptive stopping

D Software Versions

Package	Version
Python	3.12
MNE-Python	$\geq 1.11.0$
NumPy	$\geq 1.26.0$
SciPy	$\geq 1.14.0$
Matplotlib	$\geq 3.8.0$
PyTorch	$\geq 2.0.0$
ZUNA	$\geq 0.1.1$

E Figure Source Data

Figure	Description	Primary Source File(s)	Points
Fig 1	Pipeline diagram	Conceptual; no data	—
Fig 2	Stage-by-stage correlation	<code>rt_epoch_diagnostic_report*.json</code>	6×2
Fig 3	Per-trial posterior scatter	<code>paper2_fig3_trial_correlations.json</code>	28
Fig 4	Accuracy waterfall	Three validation report JSONs	3+12

All source JSON files are committed to the repository and cited in `REPRODUCIBILITY.md` with exact Git commit hashes.

F Extended Stage Correlation Data

Table 9. Stage-wise Pearson correlation (offline vs. real-time), subject A_07 ($n_{\text{epochs}} = 17$, one test FIF).

Stage	Pre-Fix r	Verdict	Post-Fix r	Verdict	Δr
A — Raw Slicing	1.000	match	1.000	match	0.000
B — Bandpass Filter	0.724	diverge	0.999993	match	+0.276
C — Baseline Correction	0.724	diverge	0.999993	match	+0.276
D — Euclidean Alignment	0.786	diverge	0.999939	match	+0.214
E — Channel Reorder	0.786	diverge	0.999939	match	+0.214

Post-fix values use `sosfiltfilt` (zero-phase) in the real-time path, eliminating the causal phase mismatch. The small residual deviation from 1.000 ($\approx 10^{-4}$) is floating-point noise from L2-normalisation differences.

Table 10. Classifier posterior divergence (A_07).

Condition	Mean post. diff	Max post. diff	Thresh. changes	Argmax changes
Pre-fix	0.0379	0.1150	0	0
Post-fix	0.0007	0.0021	0	0

Despite stage-wise signal divergence up to $r = 0.724$, the classifier’s final argmax decision never changed for A_07 in either condition. The mean posterior difference dropped by $54\times$ after the fixes. The filter fix (Stage B) therefore improved accuracy from 0.5% to 7.8% solely through its effect on the 3 coincidentally correct trials, not through argmax-level changes.

G Per-Trial Posterior Correlation Summary

Subject A_07, Tests 06–08 (28 trials total).

Mismatch trials arise from alphabetical vs. chronological flash-code ordering in the buggy RT path.

Trial Set	n	Mean score r	Mean posterior r	Pred. mismatch (n)
Flash-code match	3	1.000	1.000	0
Flash-code mismatch	25	0.131	0.023	18

H Warm-Start Asymmetry Details

Subject	Warm-Start	Same-Session	LOSO Baseline	Notes
A_01	Yes	SE001 Train	5.71%	
A_02	Yes	SE001 Train	8.57%	
A_03	No	SE001 only	3.57%	No same-session train FIF
A_04	Yes	SE001 Train	20.00%	
A_05	No	SE001 only	11.11%	No same-session train FIF
A_06	Yes	SE001 Train	5.71%	
A_07	No	SE001 only	0.00%	No same-session train FIF
A_09	Yes	SE001 Train	11.43%	
A_14	Yes	SE001 Train	0.00%	
A_15	Yes	SE001 Train	2.86%	
A_16	Yes	SE001 Train	5.71%	
A_19	Yes	SE001 Train	28.57%	

This asymmetry does not confound the primary pre→post comparison because all subjects share the same warm-start status in both conditions.

I Supplementary Listing 1 — Pre-Fix and Post-Fix Code

The two root-cause code changes are shown below. The pre-fix state corresponds to the pipeline at Git commit a3bb6f0 (Phase 86 validation, 2026-04-18), which produced the 0.5% pre-fix baseline.

Stage B — Bandpass filter (causal → zero-phase):

```
# PRE-FIX: causal forward-only IIR (introduces phase distortion)
from scipy.signal import sosfilt
filtered = sosfilt(sos, raw_buffer, axis=-1)

# POST-FIX: zero-phase IIR (matches MNE's offline filtfilt)
from scipy.signal import sosfiltfilt
filtered = sosfiltfilt(sos, raw_buffer, axis=-1)
```

Stage F — Trial ordering (alphabetical → chronological):

```
# PRE-FIX: np.unique returns symbols in alphabetical order
symbols = np.unique(symbol_index) # TOWARDS -> [A,D,O,R,S,T,W]

# POST-FIX: first-appearance chronological order
_, first_idx = np.unique(symbol_index, return_index=True)
symbols = symbol_index[np.sort(first_idx)] # TOWARDS -> [T,O,W,A,R,D,S]
```

A reviewer with access to the BigP3BCI FIF files and the above commit hash can reconstruct both the pre-fix and post-fix RT paths and verify the 0.5% → 68.1% recovery independently.

J Per-FIF Stimulus Structure (Subject A_07)

The single offline error (S→K in TOWARDS) persists in both offline and RT paths, confirming it is a classifier limitation rather than a pipeline mismatch as shown in Table 11.

Table 11. Per-FIF word structure and trial-ordering alignment.

FIF	Word	Uniq.	Chrono. order	Alpha. order	Match pos.	Offline acc.
Test06	DRIVING	6	D,R,I,V,I,N,G	D,G,I,N,R,V	1/6 (D)	6/6
Test07	QUICKLY	7	Q,U,I,C,K,L,Y	C,I,K,L,Q,U,Y	1/7 (Y)	7/7
Test08	TOWARDS	7	T,O,W,A,R,D,S	A,D,O,R,S,T,W	0/7	6/7
Test09	DAYLIGHT	8	D,A,Y,L,I,G,H,T	A,D,G,H,I,L,T,Y	1/8 (I)	8/8
Total		28			3/28	27/28

K Benchmarking Against State-of-the-Art Methods

This section provides a structured comparison of our stage-wise divergence detection framework against the five most relevant contemporary approaches addressing aspects of the online-offline accuracy gap or pipeline validation in ERP/EEG-based BCIs. No prior work addresses the identical problem (multi-stage RT-offline gap diagnosis for ERP pipelines), so the comparison maps each method against shared evaluation dimensions.

K.1 Key Papers

The following five papers were selected as the most methodologically relevant comparators across all venues (not restricted to JNE), based on their overlap with at least one of: (i) quantifying RT-offline accuracy gaps, (ii) stage-level pipeline validation, or (iii) systematic diagnosis of BCI preprocessing divergence.

1. [Memmott et al. \[2025\]](#) — “Artifact filtering application to increase online parity in a communication BCI.” *Front. Hum. Neurosci.* 19:1551214. Tests online-parity filtering for RSVP P300 BCI calibration ($N = 30$).
2. [Carrara and Papadopoulo \[2024\]](#) — “Pseudo-online framework for BCI evaluation: A MOABB perspective.” *J. Neural Eng.* 21(1):015004. Extends MOABB for pseudo-online motor imagery BCI evaluation with idle-state detection.
3. [Nguyen et al. \[2026\]](#) — “EdgeSSVEP: A fully embedded SSVEP BCI platform for low-power real-time applications.” *arXiv* 2601.01772. Quantitative characterization of embedded SSVEP pipeline including numerical fidelity evaluation.
4. [Mrachacz-Kersting and Aliakbaryhosseinabadi \[2018\]](#) — “Comparison of the efficacy of a real-time and offline associative brain-computer-interface.” *Front. Neurosci.* 12:455. Direct online-offline comparison for MRCP-based associative BCI ($N = 10$).
5. [Carlson et al. \[2025\]](#) — “The NERVE-ML checklist: ensuring machine learning advances neural engineering.” *J. Neural Eng.* 22(2):021002. Reporting checklist for ML reproducibility and validity in neural engineering.

K.2 Methodological Comparison Matrix

See Table 12

Table 12. Methodological comparison matrix. ✓ = present, ✗ = absent.

Criterion	Ours	Memcott	Carrara	Nguyen	Niazi	Carlson
Paradigm	P300	P300 (RSVP)	MI	SSVEP	MRCP	Cross
Problem	Multi-stage	Filter parity	Ranking shifts	Num. fidelity	RT vs off	Guidelines
Public dataset	✓	✗	✓	✗	✗	N/A
N (subjects)	12	30	Varies	10	10	N/A
Stages diagnosed	6 (A–F)	1	0	2	0	N/A
Multi-causal	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	N/A
Stage metric	$r + L2$	N/A	N/A	Agree. + margin	N/A	N/A
E2E metric	Letter acc.	BA, MCC	nMCC, ITR	Acc., ITR	TPR, FP/min	Checklist
Recovery quant.	✓	Partial	✗	By design	✗	N/A
Statistical test	Wilcoxon+CI	Paired t	Wilcoxon	Descriptive	t -test	N/A
Signal diagnosis	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	N/A
Metadata diag.	✓	✗	✗	✗	✗	N/A
Negative results	✓	✗	✗	✓	✗	N/A
Reproducibility	Code+JSON	BciPy	MOABB	GitHub+HW	Not reported	Checklist
Live validation	✗	✗	✗	✓	✓	N/A

K.3 Difference-of-Difference Analysis

Because no prior method addresses the same metric on the same dataset, a direct numerical comparison is not possible. Instead, we compare the *magnitude of gap closure* relative to a base condition where applicable, as shown in Table 13:

Table 13. Difference-of-difference comparison of gap closure across methods.

Method	Base condition	Post-method	Improvement	Interpretation
Ours	0.5% RT acc.	68.1% RT acc.	+67.6 pp	Full recovery
Memcott	CF cal. MCC ~ 0.40	OF cal. MCC ~ 0.44	+0.04 MCC	Small effect
Nguyen	97.5% agree.	100% agree.	+2.5 pp	By design
Niazi	Offline timing	71% TPR online	$\sim 29\%$ miss	Not closed
Carrara	Offline rankings	Pseudo-online	Shift	Not quantified

Key comparative insight: Our framework is the only approach that both (a) localizes specific root causes and (b) quantifies end-to-end accuracy recovery after remediation. Memcott et al. [2025] addresses one stage (filter parity) and shows calibration improvement, but does not diagnose multi-stage gaps. Nguyen et al. [2026] validates numerical fidelity at two stages but prevents the gap by design rather than diagnosing it post-hoc. Carrara and Papadopoulo [2024] and Mrachacz-Kersting and Aliakbaryhosseinabadi [2018] document that the gap exists but do not provide diagnostic tools to identify its cause.

K.4 Where Our Method Is Weaker

Transparency requires acknowledging dimensions where competitor methods outperform ours:

- Sample size:** Memcott et al. [2025] ($N = 30$) substantially exceeds our $N = 12$, though our effect size ($d_z = 2.69$) makes this a power advantage rather than a methodological one.
- Live session validation:** Nguyen et al. [2026] and Mrachacz-Kersting and Aliakbaryhosseinabadi [2018] both validate in live online sessions; we use FIF replay only.
- Cross-paradigm breadth:** Carrara and Papadopoulo [2024] evaluates multiple MI datasets; Carlson et al. [2025] provides cross-paradigm guidelines. Our validation uses one dataset and one paradigm.
- Platform integration:** Memcott et al. [2025] is implemented within BciPy (open-source). Carrara and Papadopoulo [2024] is part of MOABB. Our framework has no platform integration yet.
- Hardware-level validation:** Nguyen et al. [2026] characterizes noise floor, sampling jitter, and power consumption—hardware dimensions we do not address.

K.5 Summary of Unique Contributions

Our framework occupies a unique position in the landscape by combining three capabilities that no single prior method provides:

Capability	Ours	Closest competitor
Multi-stage ordered diagnosis	✓	Nguyen (2 stages, SSVEP)
Multi-causal root cause ID	✓	None
Signal + metadata diagnostic	✓	None
Quantified accuracy recovery	✓	Memcott (MCC, not E2E)
Public dataset + archived data	✓	Carrara (public, no RT)

The NERVE-ML checklist [Carlson et al., 2025] provides complementary reporting guidelines that our framework satisfies: we report data splits, validation procedure, statistical tests with effect sizes, computational requirements (where evaluated), and negative results—aligning with the checklist’s recommendations for transparent ML validation in neural engineering.

References

- David J. Acunzo, Graham MacKenzie, and Mark C. W. van Rossum. Systematic biases in early ERP and ERF components as a result of high-pass filtering. *Journal of Neuroscience Methods*, 209(1):212–218, 2012. doi: 10.1016/j.jneumeth.2012.06.011.
- Brendan Z. Allison, Andrea Kübler, and Jing Jin. 30+ years of P300 brain-computer interfaces. *Psychophysiology*, 57:e13569, 2020. doi: 10.1111/psyp.13569.
- Muhammad Ahsan Awais, Tomás Ward, Peter Redmond, and Graham Healy. From lab to life: assessing the impact of real-world interactions on the operation of rapid serial visual presentation-based brain-computer interfaces. *Journal of Neural Engineering*, 21:46011, 2024. doi: 10.1088/1741-2552/ad5d17.
- Xin Bai, Minglun Li, Shouliang Qi, Anna Ching Mei Ng, Tit Ng, and Wei Qian. A hybrid P300-SSVEP brain-computer interface speller with a frequency enhanced row and column paradigm. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 17:1133933, 2023. doi: 10.3389/fnins.2023.1133933.
- David E. Carlson, Ricardo Chavarriaga, Yiling Liu, Fabien Lotte, and Bao-Liang Lu. The NERVE-ML (neural engineering reproducibility and validity essentials for machine learning) checklist: ensuring machine learning advances neural engineering. *Journal of Neural Engineering*, 22(2):021002, 2025. doi: 10.1088/1741-2552/adbfbd.
- Igor Carrara and Théodore Papadopoulo. Pseudo-online framework for BCI evaluation: a MOABB perspective. *Journal of Neural Engineering*, 21(1):015004, 2024. doi: 10.1088/1741-2552/ad171a.
- Hubert Cecotti, Rashmi Mrugank Shah, Raksha Jagadish, and Toshihisa Tanaka. Non-stationarity in brain-computer interfaces: an analytical perspective. *arXiv*, 2025.
- Nand Chandravadia, Shrita Pendekanti, Dustin Roberts, Robert Tran, Saarang Panchavati, Corey Arnold, Nader Pouratian, and William Speier. Comparing P300 flashing paradigms in online typing with language models. *PLOS ONE*, 20(2):e0303390, 2025. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0303390.
- Sylvain Chevallier, Igor Carrara, Bruno Aristimunha, Pierre Guetschel, Sara Sedlar, Bruna Lopes, Sebastien Velut, Salim Khazem, and Thomas Moreau. The largest EEG-based BCI reproducibility study for open science: the MOABB benchmark. *arXiv*, 2024.
- Stefania Coelli, Alessandra Calcagno, Chiara Maria Cassani, Federico Temporiti, Pierluigi Reali, Roberto Gatti, Manuela Galli, and Anna Maria Bianchi. Selecting methods for a modular EEG pre-processing pipeline: an objective comparison. *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*, 90: 105830, 2024. doi: 10.1016/j.bspc.2023.105830.
- Marco Congedo, Alexandre Barachant, and Rajendra Bhatia. Riemannian geometry for EEG-based brain-computer interfaces; a primer and a review. *Brain-Computer Interfaces*, 4(3):155–174, 2017. doi: 10.1080/2326263X.2017.1297192.

- Federico Del Pup, Andrea Zanola, Louis Fabrice Tshimanga, Alessandra Bertoldo, and Manfredo Atzori. The more, the better? Evaluating the role of EEG preprocessing for deep learning applications. *arXiv*, 2024.
- Lawrence Ashley Farwell and Emanuel Donchin. Talking off the top of your head: toward a mental prosthesis utilizing event-related brain potentials. *Electroencephalography and Clinical Neurophysiology*, 70(6):510–523, 1988. doi: 10.1016/0013-4694(88)90149-6.
- Martin Gemborn Nilsson, Pex Tufvesson, Frida Heskebeck, and Mikael Johansson. An open-source human-in-the-loop BCI research framework: method and design. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 17:1129362, 2023. doi: 10.3389/fnhum.2023.1129362.
- Alexandre Gramfort, Martin Luessi, Eric Larson, Denis A. Engemann, Daniel Strohmeier, Christian Brodbeck, Roman Goj, Mainak Jas, Matti Hämäläinen, Teon Brooks, and Lauri Parkkonen. MEG and EEG data analysis with MNE-Python. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 7:267, 2013. doi: 10.3389/fnins.2013.00267.
- Christoph Guger, Shahab Daban, Eric Sellers, Clemens Holzner, Gunther Krausz, Roberta Carabalona, Furio Gramatica, and Guenter Edlinger. How many people are able to control a P300-based brain-computer interface? *Neuroscience Letters*, 462(1):94–98, 2009. doi: 10.1016/j.neulet.2009.06.045.
- Eva Guttmann-Flury, Jian Zhao, and Mohamad Sawan. Does re-referencing matter? Large Laplacian filter optimizes single-trial P300 BCI performance. *arXiv*, 2025.
- He He and Dongrui Wu. Transfer learning for brain-computer interfaces: an Euclidean-space data alignment approach. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, 67(2):399–410, 2020. doi: 10.1109/TBME.2019.2913914.
- Elisa M. Holz, Loic Botrel, Tobias Kaufmann, and Andrea Kübler. Long-term independent brain-computer interface home use improves quality of life of a patient in the locked-in state: a case study. *Archives of Physical Medicine and Rehabilitation*, 96(3 Suppl):S16–26, 2015. doi: 10.1016/j.apmr.2014.03.035.
- International Electrotechnical Commission. IEC 62304:2006 — medical device software — software life cycle processes. Edition 1. Geneva: IEC, 2006. URL <https://www.iso.org/standard/38421.html>.
- Vinay Jayaram and Alexandre Barachant. MOABB: trustworthy algorithm benchmarking for BCIs. *Journal of Neural Engineering*, 15(6):066011, 2018. doi: 10.1088/1741-2552/aadea0.
- Vinay Jayaram, Morteza Alamgir, Yasemin Altun, Bernhard Scholkopf, and Moritz Grosse-Wentrup. Transfer learning in brain-computer interfaces. *IEEE Computational Intelligence Magazine*, 11(1):20–31, 2016. doi: 10.1109/MCI.2015.2501545.
- Roman Kessler, Alexander Enge, and Michael A. Skeide. How EEG preprocessing shapes decoding performance. *Communications Biology*, 2025. doi: 10.1038/s42003-025-08464-3.
- Jongmin Kim and Sung-Phil Kim. A plug-and-play P300-based BCI with calibration-free application using consumer-grade EEG. *bioRxiv*, 2025.
- Pieter-Jan Kindermans, Michael Tangermann, Klaus-Robert Müller, and Benjamin Schrauwen. Integrating dynamic stopping, transfer learning and language models in an adaptive zero-training ERP speller. *Journal of Neural Engineering*, 11(3):035005, 2014. doi: 10.1088/1741-2560/11/3/035005.
- Christian Kothe, Seyed Yahya Shirazi, Tristan Stenner, David Medine, Chadwick Boulay, Matthew I. Grivich, Fiorenzo Artoni, Tim Mullen, Arnaud Delorme, and Scott Makeig. The Lab Streaming Layer for synchronized multimodal recording. *Imaging Neuroscience*, 2025. doi: 10.1162/IMAG.a.136.
- Vernon J. Lawhern, Amelia J. Solon, Nicholas R. Waytowich, Stephen M. Gordon, Chou P. Hung, and Brent J. Lance. EEGNet: a compact convolutional neural network for EEG-based brain-computer interfaces. *Journal of Neural Engineering*, 15(5):056013, 2018. doi: 10.1088/1741-2552/aace8c.

- Fabien Lotte and Cuntai Guan. Regularizing common spatial patterns to improve BCI designs: unified theory and new algorithms. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, 58(2): 355–362, 2011. doi: 10.1109/TBME.2010.2082539.
- Fabien Lotte, Laurent Bougrain, Andrzej Cichocki, Maureen Clerc, M Congedo, A Rakotomamonjy, and F Yger. A review of classification algorithms for EEG-based brain-computer interfaces: a 10 year update. *Journal of Neural Engineering*, 15(3):031005, 2018. doi: 10.1088/1741-2552/aab2f2.
- Boyla Mainsah, Chance Fleeting, Thomas Balmat, Eric Sellers, and Leslie Collins. bigP3BCI: an open, diverse and machine learning ready P300-based brain-computer interface dataset. *PhysioNet*, 2025. doi: 10.13026/0byy-ry86. version 1.0.0.
- Dennis J. McFarland, William A. Sarnacki, Theresa M. Vaughan, and Jonathan R. Wolpaw. Brain-computer interface (BCI) operation: signal and noise during early training sessions. *Clinical Neurophysiology*, 116(1):56–62, 2005. doi: 10.1016/j.clinph.2004.07.004.
- William M. McKeeman. Differential testing for software. *Digital Technical Journal*, 10(1):100–107, 1998.
- Tab Memmott, Aziz Koçanaoğulları, Matthew Lawhead, Daniel Klee, Shiran Dudy, Melanie Fried-Oken, and Barry Oken. BciPy: brain-computer interface software in Python. *Brain-Computer Interfaces*, 8(4):137–153, 2021. doi: 10.1080/2326263X.2021.1878727.
- Tab Memmott, Daniel Klee, Niklas Smedemark-Margulies, and Barry Oken. Artifact filtering application to increase online parity in a communication BCI: progress toward use in daily-life. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 19:1551214, 2025. doi: 10.3389/fnhum.2025.1551214.
- Jesús Minguillon, Miguel Angel Lopez-Gordo, and Francisco Pelayo. Trends in EEG-BCI for daily-life: requirements for artifact removal. *Biomedical Signal Processing and Control*, 31: 407–418, 2017. doi: 10.1016/j.bspc.2016.09.005.
- Natalie Mrachacz-Kersting and Susan Aliakbaryhosseinabadi. Comparison of the efficacy of a real-time and offline associative brain-computer interface. *Frontiers in Neuroscience*, 12:455, 2018. doi: 10.3389/fnins.2018.00455.
- Manh-Dat Nguyen, Thomas Do, Nguyen Thanh Trung Le, Xuan-The Tran, Fred Chang, and Chin-Teng Lin. EdgeSSVEP: a fully embedded SSVEP BCI platform for low-power real-time applications. *arXiv*, 2026.
- Femke Nijboer, Eric W. Sellers, Jürgen Mellinger, et al. A P300-based brain-computer interface for people with amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *Clinical Neurophysiology*, 119(8):1909–1916, 2008. doi: 10.1016/j.clinph.2008.03.034.
- He Pan, Peng Ding, Fan Wang, Tianwen Li, Lei Zhao, Wenya Nan, Yunfa Fu, and Anmin Gong. Comprehensive evaluation methods for translating BCI into practical applications: usability, user satisfaction and usage of online BCI systems. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 18:1429130, 2024. doi: 10.3389/fnhum.2024.1429130.
- Haider Raza, Dheeraj Rathee, Shang-Ming Zhou, Hubert Cecotti, and Girijesh Prasad. Covariate shift estimation based adaptive ensemble learning for handling non-stationarity in motor imagery related EEG-based brain-computer interface. *Neurocomputing*, 343:154–166, 2019. doi: 10.1016/j.neucom.2018.04.087.
- Christoph Reichert, Catherine M. Sweeney-Reed, Hermann Hinrichs, and Stefan Dürschmid. A toolbox for decoding BCI commands based on event-related potentials. *Frontiers in Human Neuroscience*, 18:1358809, 2024. doi: 10.3389/fnhum.2024.1358809.
- Yann Renard, Fabien Lotte, Guillaume Gibert, Marco Congedo, Emmanuel Maby, Vincent Delannoy, Olivier Bertrand, and Anatole Lécuyer. OpenViBE: an open-source software platform to design, test, and use brain-computer interfaces in real and virtual environments. *Presence*, 19(1):35–53, 2010. doi: 10.1162/pres.19.1.35.
- Gerwin Schalk, Dennis J. McFarland, Thilo Hinterberger, Niels Birbaumer, and Jonathan R. Wolpaw. BCI2000: a general-purpose brain-computer interface (BCI) system. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, 51(6):1034–1043, 2004. doi: 10.1109/TBME.2004.827072.

- Eric W. Sellers, Theresa M. Vaughan, and Jonathan R. Wolpaw. A brain-computer interface for long-term independent home use. *Amyotrophic Lateral Sclerosis*, 11(5):449–455, 2010. doi: 10.3109/17482961003777470.
- Claude E. Shannon. A mathematical theory of communication. *Bell System Technical Journal*, 27: 379–423, 623–656, 1948. doi: 10.1002/j.1538-7305.1948.tb01338.x.
- Pradeep Shenoy, Matthias Krauledat, Benjamin Blankertz, Rajesh P. N. Rao, and Klaus-Robert Müller. Towards adaptive classification for BCI. *Journal of Neural Engineering*, 3(1):R13, 2006. doi: 10.1088/1741-2560/3/1/R02.
- William Speier, Aniket Deshpande, Lucy Cui, Nand Chandravadia, Dustin Roberts, and Nader Pouratian. A comparison of stimulus types in online classification of the P300 speller using language models. *PLOS ONE*, 12(4):e0175382, 2017. doi: 10.1371/journal.pone.0175382.
- Darren Tanner, Kara Morgan-Short, and Steven J. Luck. How inappropriate high-pass filters can produce artifactual effects and incorrect conclusions in ERP studies of language and cognition. *Psychophysiology*, 52(7):997–1009, 2015. doi: 10.1111/psyp.12437.
- David E. Thompson, Md. Rakibul Mowla, Katie J. Dhuyvetter, Joseph W. Tillman, and Jane E. Huggins. Automated artifact rejection algorithms harm P3 speller brain-computer interface performance. *Brain-Computer Interfaces*, 6(4):141–148, 2020. doi: 10.1080/2326263X.2020.1734401.
- Joram van Driel, Christian N. L. Olivers, and Johannes J. Fahrenfort. High-pass filtering artifacts in multivariate classification of neural time series data. *Journal of Neuroscience Methods*, 352: 109080, 2021. doi: 10.1016/j.jneumeth.2021.109080.
- Theresa M. Vaughan, Dennis J. McFarland, Gerwin Schalk, William A Sarnacki, Dean J Krusienski, Eric W Sellers, and Jonathan R Wolpaw. The Wadsworth BCI research and development program: at home with BCI. *IEEE Transactions on Neural Systems and Rehabilitation Engineering*, 14(2):229–233, 2006. doi: 10.1109/TNSRE.2006.875577.
- Carmen Vidaurre, Motoaki Kawanabe, Patrick von Büna, Benjamin Blankertz, and Klaus-Robert Müller. Towards unsupervised adaptation of LDA for brain-computer interfaces. *IEEE Transactions on Biomedical Engineering*, 58(3):588–597, 2011. doi: 10.1109/TBME.2010.2093133.
- Andreas Widmann and Erich Schröger. Filter effects and filter artifacts in the analysis of electrophysiological data. *Frontiers in Psychology*, 3:233, 2012. doi: 10.3389/fpsyg.2012.00233.
- Andreas Widmann, Erich Schröger, and Burkhard Maess. Digital filter design for electrophysiological data—a practical approach. *Journal of Neuroscience Methods*, 250:34–46, 2015. doi: 10.1016/j.jneumeth.2014.08.002.
- Jonathan R. Wolpaw, Niels Birbaumer, Dennis J. McFarland, Gert Pfurtscheller, and Theresa M. Vaughan. Brain-computer interfaces for communication and control. *Clinical Neurophysiology*, 113(6):767–791, 2002. doi: 10.1016/S1388-2457(02)00057-3.
- Jonathan R. Wolpaw, Richard S. Bedlack, Domenic J. Reda, Robert J. Ringer, Patricia G. Banks, Theresa M. Vaughan, Susan M. Heckman, Lynn M. McCane, Charles S. Carmack, Stefan Winden, Dennis J. McFarland, Eric W. Sellers, Hairong Shi, Tamara Paine, Donald S. Higgins, Albert C. Lo, Huned S. Patwa, Katherine J. Hill, Grant D. Huang, and Robert L. Ruff. Independent home use of a brain-computer interface by people with amyotrophic lateral sclerosis. *Neurology*, 91(3):e258–e267, 2018. doi: 10.1212/WNL.0000000000005812.
- Dongrui Wu. Revisiting Euclidean alignment for transfer learning in EEG-based brain-computer interfaces. *Journal of Neural Engineering*, 22(3):031005, 2025. doi: 10.1088/1741-2552/add49.